

Factors Influencing the Intention to Choose Green Tourism among Young People in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Developing green tourism is necessary; this should also be the long-term orientation for Vietnamese tourism in the context of changing environmental conditions.

Objective: This study examined the influence of various factors on the intention of young people in Ho Chi Minh City to choose green tourism.

Methodology: Research data were collected from 311 samples through both direct and online surveys. The proposed model includes subjective norms, attitudes toward green tourism, perceived behavioural control, destination green image, awareness of green tourism, and environmental concerns based on multiple linear regression.

Result: The results indicate that subjective norms do not have a statistically significant effect intention of young people in Ho Chi Minh City to choose green tourism while the remaining factors positively influence the intention to choose green tourism in Ho Chi Minh City.

Conclusion: The intention to choose green tourism is strongly impacted by factors related to environmental awareness and attitudes. Environmental concern emerged as the most influential factor in green tourism intention in the standardised regression equation.

Unique Contribution: These contributions are expected to assist tourism managers and businesses in understanding the factors affecting young people's green tourism intentions, thereby enabling the development of appropriate management plans and marketing strategies.

Key Recommendation: Tourism managers and companies should implement robust communication strategies, raise public awareness about the benefits of green tourism, and develop environmentally friendly destinations.

Keywords: Green tourism; tourism; green tourism intention; Ho Chi Minh City

Introduction

Tourism has emerged as one of the most powerful economic drivers globally, contributing significantly to gross domestic product (GDP) and generating numerous employment opportunities worldwide. Tourism fosters economic growth and plays a crucial role in Vietnam's GDP, with revenues from the sector accounting for more than 9% of the national GDP in 2019 (Patiño-Toro et al., 2024). Despite being heavily impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, Vietnam's tourism sector showed strong signs of recovery in 2023, welcoming 12.6 million international tourists and 108 million domestic visitors, marking a 3.4-fold increase compared to 2022.

According to the General Statistics Office of Vietnam, tourism revenue was estimated at approximately 672 trillion VND in 2023, indicating a significant rebound from the challenges posed by the pandemic.

This highlights the critical role of domestic tourism in driving the recovery of Vietnam's tourism industry, emphasizing that the growth of the domestic tourism market is a key component of post-pandemic recovery strategies. This underscores that Vietnam has maintained and enhanced its competitive position on the global tourism map thanks to effective policies and development strategies. Although green tourism has been developed and garnered attention in many countries, it remains relatively novel in Vietnam, particularly in Ho Chi Minh City. For most of the population, the concept of "green tourism" is poorly understood, and this form of tourism has only recently attracted a small segment of public interest (Nowacki et al., 2023; Gautam, 2023). Additionally, Vietnam faces limitations in the number of organisations promoting green tourism and a scarcity of scientific research on tourist behaviour within this domain. Public awareness regarding nature conservation and environmental protection is still not at a high level, raising the question of whether green tourism can genuinely appeal to and attract widespread participation.

Green tourism is currently a trend for many domestic and foreign tourists. This type of tourism focuses on preserving landscapes and protecting the environment, maintaining biodiversity and ecological balance, limiting negative environmental impacts, and reducing plastic emissions (Chen et al., 2018). To develop sustainable tourism, green tourism is considered the top choice. It is essential to understand tourist behaviour and identify the factors influencing their intention to choose green tourism. This knowledge will enable tourism managers and businesses to develop effective management plans and marketing strategies tailored to this emerging sector. Therefore, this study examined the influence of various factors on the intention to choose green tourism among young people in Ho Chi Minh City.

Literature Review

Green tourism

Green tourism is an alternative form of tourism, often associated with rural tourism and considered a subtype of nature-based tourism. Its primary goal is to positively impact the environment while avoiding negative consequences for the ecosystems at tourist destinations (Chin et al., 2022). This has led to adopting the term "green tourism" as a substitute for other terms such as nature tourism, ecotourism, and rural tourism. Many businesses concur that any tourism activity conducted with environmental protection in mind can be categorised as green tourism (Butler, 2020).

Green tourism can be understood through four key components: (i) Environmental responsibility the need to protect, conserve, and enhance the natural and physical environment. This commitment ensures the sustainability and longevity of ecosystems, contributing to our habitats' stable and secure development. (ii) Local economic development based on promoting the long-term viability of the local economy within the framework of green tourism involves supporting local businesses, communities, and economies. This fosters sustainable economic growth and environmental sustainability, facilitating prosperity and long-term development for the region and its communities. (iii) Biodiversity and cultural diversity through green tourism values and respect for diverse cultures and their unique expressions. Doing so helps preserve and promote indigenous

cultural values, enriching the diversity of tourism experiences. This also encourages cultural appreciation and stimulation for both tourists and local communities. (iv) Enriching tourist experiences through green tourism enhances visitor experiences by encouraging active participation in nature-based activities, interactions with local residents, and deeper engagement with local cultures. This method gives travellers unique, unforgettable experiences and strengthens their connection to the local community. It fosters cultural and ecological heritage awareness (Erul & Woosnam, 2022).

Green tourism is connected with unpolluted environments like rivers, parks, woods, and other green spaces away from residential areas. This type of tourism is increasing rapidly in many nations and has several advantages over others (Gautam, 2023). Green tourism emphasizes the conservation and protection of natural resources, ecological balance, and social benefits for local communities, as well as the exploration and appreciation of a destination's natural and cultural beauty. This type of tourism also reduces trash, pollution, and ecosystem deterioration. It encourages renewable energy and recycling to improve public health. Green tourism involves visiting natural reserves, non-polluting beach activities, and environmental education, and green tourism is growing.

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) extends the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). In the TRA model, behavioural intention is the main predictor of actual conduct, which is impacted by attitude and perceived social norms (Ajzen, 1991). This framework's beliefs and social norms influence behaviour. Attitudes show how much a person likes or dislikes an object, such as an entity, action, or event. Conversely, subjective norms are an individual's evaluation of societal pressure or expectations for a behaviour. The TPB model improves on the TRA by predicting and explaining individual actions in specific circumstances and environments. The TPB predicts beliefs and behaviours in numerous contexts and is used in many study settings. This Ajzen (1991) theory explains most human behaviours by highlighting the importance of intention. Three main factors influence an individual's behavioural intentions: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, which assesses their ability to perform the behaviour given the expected challenges.

Intention to choose green tourism

Green tourism is becoming a significant trend in the tourism industry as travellers become more environmentally conscious. Positive sentiments regarding green products greatly influence tourists' intention to utilise them during vacations, according to Zhuang et al. (2021). This shows how environmental knowledge promotes sustainable tourism consumption. Kim and Han (2022) also note that subjective norms and perceived behavioural control influence travellers' green hotel choices. This shows that personal and social views and cognitive variables heavily influence tourists' decisions. Sustainable tourist development protects the environment and cultural and social values. A cultural heritage preservation study shows this twofold impact, proving that green tourism is more than a consumer trend but a deliberate strategy for sustainable tourism growth.

Theoretical framework and hypothesis development

The green image of locations strongly influences Generation Z's travel intentions. This element is the main reason young people choose green resorts. Other factors include green resort attitudes, subjective standards, and perceived behavioural control that affect their travel inclinations.

This research also helps create ecologically friendly tourism plans, which boosts the green economy and promotes sustainable tourism marketing. According to Mele et al. (2020), views concerning green products, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control, and environmental concern strongly influence young customers' green product intentions. Using the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) to examine how tourists' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control affect green tourism intentions and behaviours, tourists' awareness of green tourism and environmental concerns positively and significantly affect their attitudes. The data also show that subjective norms negatively affect travellers' green tourism intentions, while attitudes positively do. Environmental concerns influence tourist conventions and attitudes. Conversely, environmental concern and intention boost green tourism.

Verma and Chandra (2018) found that attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control affect green hotel intention. Attitude was the most critical predictor in their predictive model. Ethics and morality also influenced consumer views and inclinations to visit green hotels. Cheng et al. (2018) added that green tourism awareness affects customers' sustainable travel attitudes. Second, opinions regarding green tourism, perceived efficacy, environmental self-awareness, and destination service quality predict green tourism intention. Environmental self-awareness was the most influential. The research also showed that green tourists are more likely to travel sustainably. This indicates that green tourism goals lead to sustainable travel practices (Chuang et al., 2018).

The influence of subjective norms (SN) on the intention to choose green tourism (GI)

According to Ajzen (1991), subjective norms are an individual's beliefs about whether to do something based on the influence of loved ones. This idea defines subjective norms as societal pressure influencing a person's behaviour. Word-of-mouth from friends and relatives can cause social pressure. Word-of-mouth has become crucial in spreading environmental awareness and encouraging pro-environmental conduct in modern culture.

Numerous research studies have shown that subjective norms affect consumer behaviour, especially regarding environmental protection. According to the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), subjective standards strongly influence customers' behavioural intentions (Zhidebekkyzy et al., 2023). The study found a positive link between subjective social norms and pro-environmental behaviour, suggesting that stronger social norms promote behavioural intentions. Another study found that favourable subjective standards about buying organic food in Taiwan could increase purchase intentions, demonstrating that social and individual variables can encourage sustainable consumption (Kaur et al., 2021). The study also found that subjective standards positively affect tourists' inclinations to visit green hotels, showing that social influences affect sustainable tourism decisions.

These findings suggest that subjective norms affect food consumer behaviour and other areas, including tourism and sustainable consumption. Understanding social variables is crucial to fostering eco-friendly consumerism, and the author proposed H1 in Figure 1.

The influence of attitude toward green tourism (AT) on the intention to choose green tourism (GI)

According to Ajzen (1991), attitude is the degree to which a person views a specific action as favourable or unfavourable for executing a particular activity. Attitude is often expressed as a favourable or unfavourable appraisal of actions. Cognitive and emotive components have been suggested for this evaluation. The conceptual dimension measures the action's perceived value, whereas the emotive dimension measures enthusiasm. The study found that value-based and experiential assessments might affect an individual's attitude. According to Ajzen (1991), attitude is a key component in behavioural intention and conduct. In particular, optimistic people have more good intentions and vice versa. Numerous studies have examined tourists' general attitudes toward sustainable tourism and their specific attitudes toward selecting and using green hotel services to help the environment, as the tourism and hospitality industry emphasizes environmental protection. As shown, tourists with positive opinions toward green hotels are more likely to have positive intentions to stay at them and choose them. Attitude positively correlates with green consumption intentions in studies on ecologically responsible behaviour, and H2 in Figure 1 offers the following hypothesis.

The influence of perceived behavioural control (PBC) on the intention to choose green tourism (GI)

Along with the two criteria above, Ajzen (1991) defined "perceived behavioural control" as "an individual's perception of the ease or difficulty of performing a particular behaviour," comprised of control strength and control belief. Studies have shown that control beliefs and strengths can be viewed differently. One's self-assessment of one's ability to do the behaviour based on one's faith in facilitating or hindering variables is called control belief. It includes confidence in one's skills, traits, and external variables like luck or opportunity. When someone has more money, time, and effort, they're more likely to do something. Perceived behavioural control directly affects behavioural intention, according to numerous studies. When people appropriately assess their control, they can forecast their conduct. According to green hotel studies, perceived behavioural control strongly influences behavioural intentions. According to Bong and Jin (2017), perceived behavioural control positively correlates with intending to buy green clothing in India, and the following hypothesis, H3, is proposed in Figure 1.

The influence of destination green image (DGI) on the intention to choose green tourism (GI)

The image of a destination strongly influences travellers' travel decisions. Tourists' opinions of a destination's environmental responsibility are called its green image. This word includes tourists' environmental assessments of a destination. Management techniques, nature, landscape, wildlife, environment and climate, culture and traditions, social welfare, and commercial and hospitality amenities define a green destination. The green image of a destination influences tourists' destination selection. Recent research has examined how green visuals affect hotels, restaurants, and medium- to small-sized businesses. The study focused on hotels' green photos and eateries' green images. The study found that the green image of medium- to small-sized places can impact

tourists' travel intentions. Finally, Ashraf et al. (2020) found that tourists' intentions positively correlate with a destination's green image and proposed H4 in Figure 1 based on this foundation.

The influence of green tourism awareness (GA) on the intention to choose green tourism (GI)

Communities are growing more aware of natural resource constraints and tourism's detrimental effects. The study found that personal views, social influences, and environmental concerns influence green tourism awareness and action. Knowledge of environmental issues and sustainable tourism helps people comprehend environmental problems and the harmful effects of tourism, especially when implementing environmental protection measures. The research also found that personal understanding and environmental concerns influence the propensity to visit and revisit green hotels in the hospitality sector. Based on this, Figure 1's H5 hypothesis is offered.

The influence of environmental concern (EC) on the intention to choose green tourism (GI)

Environmental concern is an emotional engagement with environmental issues and efforts to protect the environment, such as indignation toward harm to natural ecosystems or attitudes (positive or negative) toward climate change or environmental degradation. Studies show that environmental concern reflects people's awareness of environmental issues and their willingness to participate in addressing them. Thus, environmental concern is vital to pro-environmental conduct. This study uses the behavioural framework to analyse how environmental concern affects green tourism intention.

Previous research has shown that environmentally conscious people are more inclined to act green. The study indicated that environmental concerns increased South Koreans' green hotel intentions. The survey also found that ecologically concerned Vietnamese favour green hotels. Their models include environmental concerns to expand green consumer behaviour theory. The study also found that environmental concerns affect university students' green consumption. Positive environmental concern was associated with green product intentions in the survey, and H6 is offered in Figure 1. Building upon the research and models presented in previous studies, the research model was proposed:

Source: The author suggested

Figure 1: *The framework for six critical factors influencing the intention to choose green tourism*

Figure 1 illustrates that there are six critical factors influencing the intention to choose green tourism Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam: (1) Subjective norms (SN), (2) Attitude (AT), (3) Perceived behavioral control (PBC), (4) Destination green image (DGI), (5) Green tourism awareness (GTA), (6) Environmental concern (EC), and (6) Intention to choose green tourism (GI).

Research Methods

Measurements

The measurement scales were adapted and refined to suit the research context: The sample size was determined based on Hair et al.'s (2018) recommendation, which suggests a sample size of five times the number of observed variables. The theoretical model includes 30 observed variables, requiring a minimum sample size of 150 (30*5) for analysis.

Data collection procedure

The survey targets young individuals aged 18 to 29 studying, living, and working in Ho Chi Minh City. The study employs a convenient sampling method, combining online and in-person approaches to maximise respondent accessibility. The observed variables for the research constructs are measured using a 5-point Likert scale. The research team engaged survey participants through city universities, high-tech park businesses, and previous survey participants' referrals. Once the survey data were collected, they were entered into a database and reviewed to exclude responses that did not meet the requirements, surveys with over 5% missing responses, or

non-random patterns of reactions. Ultimately, 311 valid responses were collected and analysed using SPSS 25.0 software.

Data analysis method

The survey data were analysed using SPSS 25.0 to identify the factors influencing the choice of green tourism among Ho Chi Minh City youth, ensuring objectivity and accuracy. Cronbach's Alpha reliability test was applied to evaluate the internal consistency of the scales, with variables having item-total correlation coefficients below 0.3 being excluded. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted to assess the suitability of the scales, utilizing the KMO test ($0.5 \leq \text{KMO} \leq 1$) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Sig. < 0.05). Factors with an Eigenvalue ≥ 1 were retained, and the variance explained had to exceed 50%. Multiple linear regression was used to determine the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable based on R^2 and Sig. < 0.05, while also checking for multicollinearity and autocorrelation.

Study Results

Descriptive statistics

After rigorous data screening to eliminate invalid responses, 311 valid samples met the criteria and satisfied the theoretical minimum sample size requirement. Detailed descriptive statistics of the research sample are presented in the tables below. By Gender: Among the 311 young respondents surveyed, there is a clear distinction between male and female participants. Specifically, the number of male participants is 99, accounting for 31.8%. Meanwhile, the number of female participants is 212, representing 68.2%. By Age Group: The survey results indicate the following distribution by age group. The 18–22 age group includes 30 individuals, comprising 9.6% of the total sample. The 23–25 age group constitutes the most significant proportion, with 224 individuals accounting for 72%. Lastly, the 26–29 age group comprises 57 individuals, making up 18.3%. By Occupation: The survey results also show the following distribution by occupation. The group of students accounts for 41 individuals, representing 13.2% of the total. The office employees (staff) group has the highest representation, with 138 individuals, corresponding to 44.4%. The group of general laborers comprises 51 individuals, or 16.4%. Finally, the group classified as "other occupations" includes 81 individuals, accounting for 26%.

Scale reliability by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient

The reliability and validity test results, as shown in Table 01, indicate that Cronbach's alpha values range from 0.774 to 0.834 (all exceeding the threshold of 0.7), suggesting good internal consistency. Composite reliability (CR) values range from 0.728 to 0.846, further confirming the reliability of the constructs. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values range from 0.494 to 0.709, with most constructs meeting the threshold of 0.5, indicating satisfactory convergent validity for the analysis.

Table 1: Testing reliability and validity for six critical factors influencing the intention to choose green tourism

Code	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (CR)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
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PBC (PBC1, PBC2, PBC3, PBC4)	0.789	0.836	0.561
EC (EC1, EC2, EC3, EC4)	0.774	0.816	0.526
AT (AT1, AT2, AT3, AT14)	0.834	0.822	0.537
GTA (GTA1, GTA2, GTA3, GTA4)	0.832	0.820	0.533
DGI (DGI1, DGI1, DGI1, DGI4)	0.778	0.823	0.538
SN (SN1, SN2, SN3)	0.806	0.728	0.494
GI (GI1, GI2, GI3, GI4)	0.809	0.846	0.579

Source: Data analysis results of the author

The discriminant validity test results, presented in Table 01 using cross-loading values, indicate that the measurement scales meet the criteria for discriminant validity.

Hypothesis testing of the research model

After conducting the necessary validation procedures, the regression model was well-fitted and statistically significant. The results from the regression analysis and associated tests confirmed that five key factors positively influence the intention to choose green tourism among the youth in Ho Chi Minh City. These factors are attitude toward green tourism (AT), perceived behavioural control (PBC), destination green image (DGI), green tourism awareness (GTA), and environmental concern (EC). Below is the summary table of hypothesis testing results for the research model.

Table 2: Hypothesis testing for six critical factors influencing the intention to choose green tourism

Hypothesis	Path Direction	Path Coefficient	P- values	Conclusion
<i>H₁</i>	SN → GI	0.021	0.570	<i>Rejected</i>
<i>H₂</i>	AT → GI	0.186	0.0 00	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>H₃</i>	PBC → GI	0.121	0.002	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>H₄</i>	DGI → GI	0.237	0.000	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>H₅</i>	GTA → GI	0.226	0.000	<i>Accepted</i>
<i>H₆</i>	EC → GI	0.350	0.000	<i>Accepted</i>

Source: Data analysis results of the author

From the results in Table 02, the relationship between subjective norms (SN) and the intention to choose green tourism (GI) was not statistically significant. The remaining relationships were all significant and showed positive correlations. This indicates that a one-point increase (or decrease) in the average score of these factors will result in a corresponding increase (or decrease) in the intention to choose green tourism among the youth in Ho Chi Minh City. Among these relationships, the most substantial impact is observed in the path EC → GI ($\beta = 0.350$), suggesting that environmental concern plays the most significant role in influencing green tourism choices among the youth. The remaining relationships exhibit impact coefficients ranging from 0.121 to 0.237.

Discussion of Findings

The model showed that all factors except subjective norms (SN), which were insignificant, significantly affected the Ho Chi Minh City youth's intention to select green tourism. Environmental understanding and attitudes substantially influence green tourism (GI) intention. Environmental concern (EC) had the most significant impact on green tourism intention in the standardised regression equation, with a coefficient of 0.350. The study illuminates key elements influencing Ho Chi Minh City youth ecotourism choices. The most important factor is environmental concern (EC), which suggests that younger generations, more environmentally conscious, prefer eco-friendly vacation packages. This discovery emphasises the necessity of environmental awareness programs and public education to protect the world. The green image of destinations (DGI) also significantly impacted, suggesting that eco-friendly places are more appealing.

Destination green image (DGI) exhibited a coefficient of 0.237, supporting Nowacki et al. (2023). A site with a strong green image encourages green tourism, helping establish sustainable tourism models. According to studies, green tourism awareness (GTA) had a favourable effect with a coefficient of 0.226. Green tourism is more likely to be supported by tourists who appreciate its benefits and practices. Verma and Chandra (2018) found coefficients of 0.186 and 0.121 for attitude toward green tourism (AT) and perceived behavioural control (PBC). Tourists engage in green tourism when they feel confident and optimistic (Erul & Woosnam, 2022).

With specific contextual changes, such as the limited significance of subjective norms, the results support applying the Theory of Planned Behaviour to understand green tourism objectives (Gautam 2023; Ashraf et al., 2020). The report suggests stakeholders increase environmental education, use green branding, and remove practical barriers to involvement. Vietnam's tourist industry aims for sustainable development, and these measures will promote green tourism.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Theory and practice are examined in this study of young adults' green tourism intentions in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. The results show that environmental concern, destination green image, green tourism awareness, attitude, and perceived behavioral control strongly affect green tourism intentions. Environmental concern is the most important, emphasizing the importance of ecological understanding in sustainable tourism. This cohort's green tourism decisions were autonomous primarily, as subjective standards had no significant effect. This study suggests contextual adaptation is needed when examining sustainability decisions in culturally diverse situations, deviating from typical Theory of Planned Behaviour applications. The findings show that green tourism is growing in Vietnam's tourism sector, offering a development opportunity. Vietnam is developing green tourism, which will soon become a mainstream trend. This allows businesses and tourist operators to improve their service and promotion to attract customers. The study found that environmental concern, destination green image, and green tourism awareness influence green tourism intention. Tourism managers and organisations should communicate effectively, promote green tourism, and create eco-friendly places to encourage this trend. These measures will draw tourists and preserve the tourism industry. Results offer the following policy recommendations:

(1) Environmental concern (EC → GI; $\beta = 0.350$, $P = 0.000$). EC has the greatest impact on green tourism intention, emphasizing the importance of environmental consciousness. Large-scale awareness initiatives concerning environmental issues and green tourism are recommended. Work with influencers and environmental groups to tell engaging ecological conservation stories. Community involvement in environmental protection activities like beach clean-ups and tree planting can improve awareness and attract green tourism. Tourism businesses should adopt eco-certifications and promote them in marketing materials to attract environmentally concerned tourists.

(2) Destination green image (DGI → GI; $\beta = 0.237$, $P = 0.000$). A destination's green image encourages ecotourism. To brand green places, use visual storytelling to emphasize unspoiled nature, clean habitats, and sustainable methods. Promote eco-friendly services like electric vehicle charging stations, garbage recycling systems, and green architecture to boost destination attractiveness. Strategic partnerships involve ecotourism providers and local governments to link the green image with sustainable development goals.

(3) Green tourism awareness (GTA → GI; $\beta = 0.226$, $P = 0.000$). Awareness of green tourism benefits strongly influences customer choices. Educational workshops on sustainable tourism should be interactive in schools, colleges, and communities. Social media and traditional marketing strategies highlight green tourism benefits like lower environmental impact and unique cultural experiences. Develop mobile apps or websites with quizzes, games, and green tourism ideas to engage young audiences and raise awareness.

(4) Attitude Toward Green Tourism (AT → GI; $\beta = 0.186$, $P = 0.000$). Positive attitudes toward green tourism boost behavioural intentions. Positive advertising efforts should highlight green tourism's emotional and sensory benefits, such as reconnecting with nature and preserving the environment. Influencer engagement involves working with travel bloggers, vloggers, and social media influencers to promote green tourism. Green reward programs, such as discounts for eco-friendly travel packages or points for sustainable deeds, encourage positive behaviour.

(5) Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC → GI; $\beta = 0.121$, $P = 0.002$). Decisions about green tourism depend on perceived ease or difficulty. Green tourism should be affordable and accessible. Offer group booking discounts or affordable packages. Mobile apps and websites simplify green tourism booking for tourists. Information transparency reduces perceived barriers by offering clear, complete information on eco-friendly measures and how they improve tourism.

Limitations and future research: The research only includes young people in Ho Chi Minh City, which may limit its application to other places or age groups in Vietnam. Future studies should focus on urban and rural residents to represent a more diverse demographic. Comparing urban and rural areas might illuminate green tourism behaviours in different cultural and environmental contexts. Since participants were mostly from schools and workplaces, convenience sampling can skew and reduce sample representativeness. Future studies will use stratified random sampling to represent the population more fairly. Longitudinal studies could also track green tourism aspirations over time for extra insights.

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